

Discrete perturbation theory for Mie potentials

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Abstract

The Discrete Perturbation approach in its version for soft–core continuous potentials is applied to a family of Mie (α , γ) potentials. Within this approach, once a discrete version of the potential is given, only the knowledge of the square–well Helmholtz free–energy perturbation terms are required to obtain the Helmholtz free–energy for the discrete version of the original potential. The free–energy so obtained is analytical and expressed as a function of density, temperature and the intermolecular parameters, and from it all thermodynamic properties can be obtained in a straightforward way. By varying the exponents α and γ some illustrative cases of Mie fluids are considered. Single state pressures and the vapor– liquid phase diagram are obtained and compared with simulation data. The best performance of this equation of state is achieved at supercritical states and when the vapor–liquid phase diagram appears at not so low temperatures. Within this approach the corresponding states principle is analyzed. The methodology presented can be useful to study other families of potentials models for simple and complex fluids.

I. INTRODUCTION

The interest in trying to model the fluid thermodynamic behavior of real systems within the frame of Statistical Mechanics using simple effective potentials is still a challenging problem. Concerning pair-wise spherical potentials, a good model example is the Mie potential $\Phi_{Mie}(r)$.¹ This potential is able to describe the main features of fluid phases when the van-der-Waals attraction² at long distances and the repulsion at short distances caused by the overlapping of electronic clouds are the leading terms in the intermolecular interaction. The reduced Mie potential $\phi_{Mie}(r)$ between two particles separated by a distance r is given by:

$$\phi_{Mie}(r) = \frac{\Phi_{Mie}(r)}{\epsilon} = C_{\alpha\gamma} \left[\left(\frac{\sigma}{r} \right)^\alpha - \left(\frac{\sigma}{r} \right)^\gamma \right], \quad (1)$$

with

$$C_{\alpha\gamma} = \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha - \gamma} \right) \left(\frac{\alpha}{\gamma} \right)^{\gamma/(\alpha-\gamma)}, \quad (2)$$

where σ is the distance at which the potential is zero, ϵ is the minimum of the potential energy and α and γ are real numbers (in general selected as integers) that modulate the (hard or soft) repulsive and (short- or long- ranged) attractive interactions, respectively. A very interesting historical review of the development of this potential can be found in Laffite et al.³ work. A particular important case of this family of potentials is the well known Lennard-Jones potential that can be described by a Mie potential with $\alpha = 12$ and $\gamma = 6$.⁴ This potential has been one of the most important pair potential for the description of fluids in statistical mechanics. Besides, most of the force field libraries in free and commercial simulation software for atom–atom (or molecule–molecule) interactions use this model potential, among a few others.^{5–13}

Recently, some interest has emerged in considering other combinations of α and γ values in order to model a wider variety of systems in simple fluid theories and in more complex ones, as for instance, for modeling the monomer–monomer interactions in the Mie Statistical Associated Fluid Theory (SAFT-Mie).^{3,14} Many efforts using mainly perturbation theory and simulations have been performed to better understand the phase diagram and their applications to real fluids.^{3,14–32} Ramrattan et al.¹⁶ have made extensive simulations studies to

cover the complete phase diagram (vapor–liquid–solid) of a variety of Mie potentials. Besides, based on their simulation results they have found a parameter ξ (in their work denoted as α) expressed in terms of the Mie exponents that can define the Mie potential subfamilies that follow the principle of corresponding states.^{33,34} This finding contradicts some authors that based also on simulation studies say that Mie potentials follow the principle of corresponding states, at least for the cases that they have considered.^{19,22,35,36} After reading the works of Laffite et al.³ and Ramrattan et al.¹⁶ it seems that everything has been solved for these Mie potentials and there is not too much to do to improve their results. However, their results are valid only for Mie potentials and it is important to have an available methodology that could be useful not only for them but other interesting family of potentials. This is the aim of this work. The formalism is based on the Statistical Mechanics perturbation theory.^{37,38}

The Discrete Perturbation Theory (DPT)³⁹ and its extension to binary mixtures,⁴⁰ polar,⁴¹ and molecular fluids^{42,43} represents a useful efficient tool to generate analytical expressions for the Helmholtz free–energy in terms of density, temperature and the intermolecular parameters characterizing the interaction. So from this free–energy expression all thermodynamic properties can be easily obtained using the common thermodynamic relations. Although, by construction DPT uses the hard sphere as reference potential, it also provides good approximations for the thermodynamic properties of soft-core potentials, as for example, Lennard–Jones, Kihara and Franzese potential.^{42,44,45} In fact, DPT can be applied to intermolecular potential models that can be described as a good approximation as a sum of a sequence of square-shoulders and square–wells steps. Its main advantage is that it only requires the knowledge of an analytical expression for the hard–sphere Helmholtz free–energy and for the square-well (SW) perturbation terms as a function of the square well range, λ_{SW} , and the density. Concerning the hard–sphere there are different available expressions. For the SW perturbation terms there are some analytical expressions available in the literature.^{46–54} One advantage of the DPT approach is that it can be improved in the future as long as better expressions for the perturbation SW terms are provided. For the soft–core potentials one also needs to evaluate an effective diameter to construct an approximated hard-core system. For simplicity, as a good approximation one can choose for instance the Barker and Henderson diameter.^{38,55,56} In this work we apply the DPT to Mie potentials for variable sets of exponents (α, γ) . To investigate the performance of this

equation we compare its predictions for the vapor–liquid phase diagram and super critical pressures with available and new (obtained in this work) simulation data. Finally, some analysis is included to investigate if DPT for the Mie potential for any set of exponents α and γ follows a corresponding states behavior or not.

II. DPT FOR MIE POTENTIALS

DPT for soft–core continuous potentials can be implemented for the Mie potentials as follows:

1) An approximated hard–core Mie potential version is required. This can be done with an effective diameter that accounts for the potential softness. One possibility, among others, is to obtain this effective diameter by using the Barker and Henderson procedure:^{55,56}

$$d_{BH}(T^*) = \int_0^\sigma dr \left[1 - \exp \left(-\frac{1}{T^*} \phi_{Mie}(r) \right) \right]. \quad (3)$$

In this expression $T^* = k_B T / \epsilon$, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, and T is the absolute temperature. With this effective diameter the hard–core Mie potential, $\phi_{HCMie}(x)$, takes the form:

$$\phi_{HCMie}(x) = \begin{cases} \infty & \text{if } x \leq 1 \\ C_{\alpha\gamma} \left[\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)^\alpha - \left(\frac{1}{x}\right)^\gamma \right] & \text{if } x > 1, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $x = r/d_{BH}$.

2) A discrete version of this hard–core potential with effective diameter is needed and it can be built in the following way:

a) One needs to identify the length of the discretization interval, $I = (\lambda_c - \lambda_0)$, with $\lambda_0 = 1$ being the reduced potential contact value and λ_c being the reduced cutoff distance. One should notice that the scaling parameter to reduce distances is now d_{BH} .

b) The partition width of the interval I is selected $w = \lambda_i - \lambda_{i-1}$. This selection depends on the form of the potential, for instance, w should be smaller if the number of potential sign derivative changes increases. The number of discretizations, for a fixed width selection is determined with the above parameters, $n = nint[I/w]$, with $nint$ being the nearest integer

number. For each interval $[\lambda_{i-1}, \lambda_i]$ one needs to select an energy ϵ_i . A possible natural selection is to take the midpoint of each interval to evaluate the corresponding energy.

c) The discrete version of the reduced Mie potential, with the midpoint selection, is given as (see Fig. 1):

$$\phi_{HCMie}^{Dis}(x) = \begin{cases} \infty & \text{if } x \leq 1 \\ C_{\alpha\gamma} \left[\left(\frac{1}{\lambda_0 + (2j-1)\frac{w}{2}} \right)^\alpha - \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_0 + (2j-1)\frac{w}{2}} \right)^\gamma \right] & \text{if } \lambda_0 + (j-1)w < x \leq \lambda_0 + jw \\ 0 & \text{if } x > \lambda_c. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

It is pertinent to say that one could also choose a variable width partition, in that case, the above relations still hold for each partition.

FIG. 1: Example of a hard-core Mie potential (blue line) and its discrete version (black line). Here $\epsilon_j^* = \epsilon_j/\epsilon$.

3) For a system of N particles interacting with a given discrete Mie potential (α and γ settled) in a volume V , at reduced temperature $T^* = \frac{kT}{\epsilon}$, and density $\rho^\dagger = \rho d_{BH}^3$, the DPT

reduced excess Helmholtz free-energy, $a^{ex} \equiv \frac{A^{ex}}{Nk_B T}$, can be obtained as:³⁹

$$\begin{aligned}
a^{ex}(\rho^\dagger, T^*) &= a_{HS}(\rho^\dagger) + \frac{1}{T^*} \sum_{j=1}^n [a_1^S(\rho^\dagger, \lambda_j, \epsilon_j^*) - a_1^S(\rho^\dagger, \lambda_{j-1}, \epsilon_j^*)] \\
&+ \frac{1}{T^{*2}} \sum_{j=1}^n [a_2^S(\rho^\dagger, \lambda_j, \epsilon_j^*) - a_2^S(\rho^\dagger, \lambda_{j-1}, \epsilon_j^*)] \\
&+ \frac{1}{T^{*3}} \sum_{j=1}^n [a_3^S(\rho^\dagger, \lambda_j, \epsilon_j^*) - a_3^S(\rho^\dagger, \lambda_{j-1}, \epsilon_j^*)] + \dots,
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where $\epsilon_j^* = \epsilon_j/\epsilon$, the a_i^S are the i -th free-energy perturbation terms of an S potential, where S denotes either a square-well (SW) ($\epsilon_j < 0$) or a square-shoulder (SS) ($\epsilon_j > 0$). Within this approach the following relation is assumed:

$$a_i^{SS}(\rho^\dagger, \lambda_i, \epsilon_i) = (-1)^i a_i^{SW}(\rho^\dagger, \lambda_i, \epsilon_i). \tag{7}$$

This assumption simplifies the evaluation of the Helmholtz free-energy since, as can be seen, Eq. (6) only requires the knowledge of $a_{HS}(\rho^\dagger)$ and $a_i^{SW}(\rho^\dagger, \lambda_{SW})$ terms. For some of these terms there are analytical expressions available in the literature as a function of density and SW potential range λ_{SW} .^{46–54,57–62}

Once we have the analytical expressions for these HS and SW terms, the step width and the cutoff distance chosen for a given set of Mie exponents, Eq. (6) can be expressed in the following simple form:

$$a^{ex}(\rho^\dagger, T^*) \equiv a_{HS}(\rho^\dagger) + \frac{a_1(\rho^\dagger)}{T^*} + \frac{a_2(\rho^\dagger)}{T^{*2}} + \frac{a_3(\rho^\dagger)}{T^{*3}} + \dots, \tag{8}$$

where the a_i terms become only density dependent.

4) From Eq. (8) the determination of other thermodynamic properties is straightforward using standard thermodynamic relations such as the compressibility factor $Z = \rho^\dagger \left(\frac{\partial a}{\partial \rho^\dagger} \right)_{T^*}$ and the reduced internal energy $u = -T^* \left(\frac{\partial a}{\partial T^*} \right)_{\rho^\dagger}$. These properties then can also be expressed as a high-temperature expansion as:

$$Z(\rho^\dagger, T^*) = 1 + z_{HS}(\rho^\dagger) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{z_n(\rho^\dagger)}{T^{*n}} \tag{9}$$

and

$$u(\rho^\dagger, T^*) = u^{Id}(T^*) + u_{HS}(T^*) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{u_n(\rho^\dagger)}{T^{*n}}, \tag{10}$$

with $z_i = \rho^\dagger \left(\frac{\partial a_i}{\partial \rho^\dagger} \right)$ and $u_i = -T^* \left(\frac{\partial a_i}{\partial T^*} \right)$. The explicit expressions for the ideal, hard-sphere, z_i , and u_i are given in the Appendix A.

The reduced pressure and the reduced chemical potential can be computed by using the definitions $P^\dagger = \frac{P d_{BH}^3}{|\epsilon|} = Z \rho^\dagger T^*$ and $\mu^* = \mu/k_B T = \frac{\partial(a \rho^\dagger)}{\partial \rho^\dagger} = a + Z$, respectively.

Besides, by solving for a given temperature the conventional vapor–liquid coexistence conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} P^\dagger(\rho_l^\dagger) &= P^\dagger(\rho_g^\dagger), \\ \mu^*(\rho_l^\dagger) &= \mu^*(\rho_g^\dagger), \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

one can obtain the gas (ρ_g^\dagger) and liquid (ρ_l^\dagger) coexistence densities.

In order to compare with the simulation data, it is necessary to express the previous results in the conventional reduced units, given by:

$$\begin{aligned} P^* &= P^\dagger / d_{BH}^{*3}, \\ \rho^* &= \rho^\dagger / d_{BH}^{*3}, \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

where $P^* = \frac{P \sigma^3}{|\epsilon|}$, $\rho^* = \rho \sigma^3$, and $d^* = d_{BH} / \sigma$.

III. RESULTS

We consider some Mie–potential illustrative cases in order to show the reliability of the DPT approach. We have selected the cases: $(\alpha, 6)$ with $\alpha = 8, 12, 18, 32$; $(14, 7)$, $(18, 9)$, $(9.85, 6)$, $(14.65, 8)$, $(15.58, 6)$, $(20, 5.11)$, $(50, 4.05)$, and $(50, 4.52)$. In Table I the Mie coefficients $C_{\alpha\gamma}$ for each case are shown.

As a first stage, we have obtained the Barker and Henderson diameter for the Mie potential, given by Eq. (1), by solving numerically Eq. (3) for reduced temperatures $T^* \leq 15$. The variation of d_{BH} with T^* for the Mie potentials are plotted in Fig. 2. As expected, d_{BH} for the Mie family decreases as the temperature increases for all cases. For $\gamma = 6$ and variable α this behavior is more evident when the potential is smoother. At the maximum temperature $T^* = 6$ considered one notices that for the extreme cases $(50, 4.52)$ and $(8, 6)$ the diameter diminishes (respect to the hard-core case) approximately 3 % and 10 %, respectively. However, notice that for α fixed the variation in γ also has an effect on the

Barker-Henderson diameter and less obvious, notice that for the cases $\alpha = 18$ fixed and $\gamma = 9$ and 6, the case (18, 6) corresponds to a softer system (smaller diameter).

FIG. 2: Numerical values of the reduced Barker-Henderson diameter, $d_{BH}^* = d_{BH}/\sigma$, for the Mie potentials studied in this work.

There are different analytical approximated expressions for the Barker-Henderson diameter for the Lennard–Jones case, Mie (12, 6), such as the Cotterman et al.,⁶³ Souza and Ben-Amotz,⁶⁴ and Sun Jiu-Xun,⁶⁵ but to our knowledge, there are not available for other (α, γ) cases. For simplicity we have selected a fourth-order polynomial fit (see coefficients in Table I) for all Mie cases studied in this work, however, other approximations could be explored.

The second stage involves the definition of the discrete version, ϕ_{HCMie}^{Dis} , Eq. 5, for a given set of Mie exponents. So it requires the values of λ_c and w for each case. The step width for all cases considered was chosen as $w = 0.07$. The cutoff distance λ_c was chosen at the distance for which the value of the reduced potential is such that $\phi_{Mie}(\lambda_c) \sim (-10^{-6})$. The corresponding values for each case are also reported in Table I.

TABLE I: Mie Coefficients $C_{\alpha\gamma}$, Barker and Henderson diameter coefficients d_i for the fourth-order polynomial fit for each case considered. In the last column we included the Hard-Core Mie cut-off distance λ_c .

α	γ	$C_{\alpha\gamma}$	$d_1 10^{-2}$	$d_2 10^{-3}$	$d_3 10^{-4}$	$d_4 10^{-6}$	λ_c
8	6	9.48	-3.556	4.880	-3.572	9.72	15
12	6	4.00	-2.826	3.893	-2.856	7.78	13
18	6	2.60	-2.182	3.040	-2.241	6.12	12
32	6	1.81	-1.453	2.075	-1.545	4.24	12
14	7	4.00	-2.441	3.360	-2.466	6.72	9
18	9	4.00	-1.925	2.650	-1.949	5.32	6
9.85	6	5.54	-3.172	4.358	-3.192	8.69	14
14.65	8	4.56	-2.267	3.112	-2.284	6.23	7
15.58	6	2.96	-2.400	3.328	-2.448	6.68	12
20.00	5.11	2.15	-2.282	4.192	-4.338	17.00	18
50.00	4.05	1.36	-1.139	2.158	-2.257	8.89	33
50.00	4.52	1.40	-1.123	2.120	-2.215	8.72	23

With this information, one can now evaluate Eq. (6) to fourth-order by using the expressions for the a_{HS} and a_i^{SW} terms. For the HS sphere term, we selected the well-known Carnahan and Starling equation of state.⁶⁰ For the SW terms we have selected the a_i^{SW} for $i = 1, \dots, 4$ of Espíndola et al.⁵⁰ for ranges $1.07 < \lambda < 3$. For longer ranges, $\lambda > 3$, we used a_1^{SW} of F. del Rio and L. Lira,⁴⁷ a_2^{SW} of Benavides and del Río,⁵³ and $a_3^{SW} = a_4^{SW} = 0$. The analytical expressions for these terms are reported in the original references but in order to make this work self contained we have included them in the Appendix A.

We have calculated single pressures as a function of density for several supercritical isotherms and compared them with available and new simulation data for different Mie potentials. The new simulation data for Mie (32, 6) and Mie (14.65, 6) complements the reported one and are shown in Table II. These simulations were performed in NVT Molecular Dynamics using 1000 particles in a cubic box with periodic boundary conditions. The com-

ponents of the initial velocities are computed pseudo-randomly from a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution and the moment of the center of mass is removed. The equations of motion are integrated using the Verlet algorithm with a dimensionless timestep of 0.004. We used 10^5 timesteps for equilibration prior to the computation of the averages of pressures using the subblock average method with 10 subblocks, each one composed of 10^5 timesteps to avoid correlations on the statistics. Velocity scaling was used to control the temperature. These properties were computed using a cutoff distance of $r_{cut}^* = 4.0$ and adding analytical long range corrections (*lrc*):

$$P_{lrc}^* = \frac{2}{3}\pi\rho^{*2}C_{\alpha\gamma} \left[\frac{\alpha}{\alpha-3} \left(\frac{1}{r_{cut}^*}\right)^{\alpha-3} - \frac{\gamma}{\gamma-3} \left(\frac{1}{r_{cut}^*}\right)^{\gamma-3} \right]. \quad (13)$$

We have found that the best performance of the DPT was reached for reduced temperatures above or equal one. In Fig. 3, several pressure *vs* density supercritical isotherms are compared with available^{22,66,67} and new simulation data obtained in this work, see Table II. In order to make an easier comparison against SAFT-VR MIE (see Figure 9 in Laffite et al.³), in (a)-(e) we considered the following temperatures in (a) $T^* = 1.567, 1.960, 2.476$; (b) $T^* = 1.219, 1.523, 1.904$; (c) $T^* = 1.29234, 1.60734, 2.016525$; (d) $T^* = 0.8985, 1.1230, 1.4040$; (e) $T^* = 1.6635, 1.3308, 1.0646$. In the figure the temperature labels are shown rounded as in Laffite et al.³ to make an easier comparison. As can be seen the DPT predictions are good when compared with simulation data and for most of the cases it gives comparable results than those of SAFT Mie theory. We have included in (f) a non-integer exponent Mie potential case to show that DPT works also for non integer Mie exponents.

FIG. 3: Pressure–density isotherms for Mie (α, γ) potentials as predicted by DPT (continuous line). (a)-(e) show the (12, 6), (14, 7), (18, 6), (18, 9), and (32, 6) Mie cases, respectively. We have included the simulation data of Orea et al.^{22,66} (filled circles), this work simulation ones (filled squares), and in (a) diamonds are simulation data from Johnson et al.⁶⁷ In (f) we present a non-integer exponent case: Mie (14.65, 8) potential and this work simulation data (filled squares).

TABLE II: This work simulation results for super critical pressures as a function of density for Mie (32, 6) and Mie (14.65, 6) potentials.

Mie (32, 6)			Mie (14.65, 6)		
T^*	ρ^*	P^*	T^*	ρ^*	P^*
2.0	0.2	0.434(1)	1.5	0.2	0.28(0)
	0.4	1.128(3)		0.4	0.648(1)
	0.6	2.737(9)		0.6	1.558(3)
	0.8	7.24 (2)		0.8	4.560(7)
4.0	0.2	1.027(2)	2.5	0.2	0.575(1)
	0.4	2.928(5)		0.4	1.525(1)
	0.6	7.04 (1)		0.6	3.618(5)
	0.8	16.67(4)		0.8	8.91 (1)

The calculation of liquid-vapor phase boundaries that arise from the conditions of thermal, mechanical, and chemical equilibrium constitutes a more severe proof for any equation of state since it tests not only the free-energy equation of state, but also their first derivatives respect to volume (pressure) and number of particles (chemical potential). In Fig. 4 DPT predictions are compared with Monte Carlo and Molecular Dynamics simulation data. Both liquid and gas branches of the curve are accurately described within our theoretical framework, even for non-integer values of the exponents describing the potential. As expected from a high temperature perturbation-based theory, its performance is better for high temperatures and the critical parameters are systematically overestimated. However, one of the advantages of this approach is that it can be improved in the future when better approximations for the a_i^{SW} terms will be developed. This information would benefit this theory towards an analytical and accurate equation of state able to describe the characteristic asymptotic behavior in the critical region.

FIG. 4: DPT predictions for the liquid-vapor coexistence for Mie (α, γ) potential (continuous line). (a) Mie (12, 6) potential; simulation data from Ramrattan et al.,¹⁶ Okumura and Yonezawa,¹⁹ Orea et al.,²² Alejandro and Trokhymchuk,²⁹ and Lofti et al.³²; (b) Mie $(\alpha, 6)$ potentials with $\alpha = 8, 9.85, 12, 15.58$ and the case (14, 7); simulation data from Ramrattan et al.¹⁶ except that for the case (14, 7) is from Nasrabad²¹ and for the case (12, 6) that is from Trokhymchuk and Alejandro.²⁹

We also have analyzed the validity of the corresponding states principle for the Mie potentials. Based on simulation studies, Orea et al.²² and Okumura and Yonezawa,¹⁹ suggested that the whole Mie family follows the corresponding states principle independently of the values of the repulsive and attractive exponents. This conclusion was obtained considering the vapor-liquid coexistence curves. Recently, Ramrattan et al.¹⁶ also with simulation techniques explored the vapor-liquid-solid phase diagram, for several Mie potentials. They have found that the corresponding states principle is only satisfied for Mie potentials sharing the same value of a parameter ξ (denoted as α in the original work), which is a dimensionless parameter that is only a function of the repulsive and attractive exponents:

$$\xi = C_{\alpha\gamma} \left[\left(\frac{1}{\gamma - 3} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{\alpha - 3} \right) \right]. \quad (14)$$

Ramrattan et al.¹⁶ using this parameter found a linear parametrization for the critical and triple point temperatures for these systems.

In order to identify the ξ values for which DPT predicts accurate critical densities and temperatures, in Table III DPT critical properties for different Mie potentials and their corresponding ξ value are shown together with available critical simulation data. In this

Table we have considered only Mie cases whose critical temperature simulation data is greater than one, since one expects that a high temperature perturbation expansion will give better results for high temperatures. As can be seen in this Table and in Fig. 5, the DPT critical temperatures are in good agreement with simulation data for $\xi > 0.85$ (except for the point $\xi = 1.264$ of Okumura and Yonezawa¹⁹) and they deviate at most around 8% for $\xi > 0.63$.

TABLE III: Critical properties for the Mie potentials and parameter ξ . Data from DPT and simulation from Ramrattan et al.¹⁶ (RAM), Okumura and Yonezawa¹⁹ (OY), Orea et al.²² (ORD), Nasrabad²¹ (NAS) and Panagiotopoulos²⁸ (PAN).

Mie	ξ	ρ_c^*	T_c^*	P_c^*	Data
(8, 6)	1.264	0.3011	1.724	0.1917	DPT
		0.298(2)	1.814(5)	0.170(1)	OY
		0.296	1.743		RAM
(50, 4.05)	1.264	0.3007	1.7450	0.1981	DPT
(9.85, 6)	1.038	0.2990	1.484	0.1646	DPT
		0.293	1.456		RAM
(12, 6)	0.890	0.3011	1.329	0.1458	DPT
		0.314(6)	1.290(9)	0.118(3)	ORD
		0.316	1.299	0.125	PAN
		0.304(2)	1.313(2)	0.125(1)	OY
		0.312	1.312	0.119	RAM
(20, 5.11)	0.890	0.3064	1.351	0.1561	DPT
(50, 4.52)	0.890	0.3118	1.372	0.1635	DPT
(15.58, 6)	0.750	0.3074	1.190	0.1373	DPT
		0.324	1.113		RAM
(18, 6)	0.693	0.3124	1.133	0.1331	DPT
		0.330(5)	1.050(6)	0.102(2)	ORD
		0.320(4)	1.072(2)	0.106(1)	OY
		0.33	1.071	0.106	PAN
(14, 7)	0.636	0.3113	1.064	0.1243	DPT
		0.3278	0.9941	0.090	NAS
		0.330(8)	0.990(7)	0.098(2)	ORD

FIG. 5: Critical temperature as a function of the parameter ξ proposed in Ramrattan et al.¹⁶ work for the Mie cases considered in this work. Simulation data (filled circles) from Ramrattan et al.,¹⁶ Okumura and Yonezawa,¹⁹ Nasrabad,²¹ Orea et al.,²² Trokhymchuk and Alejandre,²⁹ and Lofti et al.,³² DPT predictions are shown with an asterisk symbol. Linear fit¹⁶ for simulation data (indigo line) and for theoretical data (black line) are plotted.

Now that we know where DPT reproduces the simulation critical temperatures and densities, $\xi > 0.85$, we will investigate if Mie potentials follow a corresponding states behavior. For this analysis we will consider Mie potentials classified by the ξ parameter.

A. Temperature–density fluid coexistence curves

1. Families of Mie potentials with same ξ value

The vapor-liquid coexistence curves are presented in Fig. 6. In Fig. 6(a), the coexistence curves for two pairs of Mie potentials are shown, the pair (12, 6) and (9.16, 7) for which $\xi = 0.89$, and the pair (8, 6) and (9.29, 5.5) with $\xi = 1.264$. Notice that the coexistence curves are very similar for potentials with the same ξ value. An explanation for this is that these two sets of potentials with the same ξ value are very similar in shape (see Fig. 7) so it is not surprising that their corresponding coexistence curves should be almost identical, even

if in the plot the density and the temperature are not reduced with respect to the critical properties. After this finding, we explored other possible combinations of exponents with the same ξ value. We found that there are some sets of exponents that produce potentials with almost the same graphical appearance and obviously these potentials will follow a corresponding states behavior. However we found cases of Mie potentials with the same ξ value for which the graphical appearance is different, as for example, (12, 6), (20, 5.11) and (50, 4.52), characterized by $\xi = 0.89$ (see Fig. 8(a)). For these cases DPT predicts that they do not follow the corresponding states principle, as can be seen in figure 8(b), where their vapor-liquid phase diagrams are shown. This result contradicts previous conclusions based on simulations, suggesting that either all Mie potentials^{19,22} or Mie potentials with the same ξ value¹⁶ follow a corresponding states principle. The last two cases have not been previously studied by simulations but for them we expect a good behavior of the DPT since their reduced critical temperatures are greater than one and $\xi = 0.89$.

FIG. 6: Vapor-liquid coexistence curves for several Mie potential characterized by the factor ξ as in Ramrattan et al.¹⁶ work. (a) Comparison between two potentials with same value of ξ . (b) Vapor-liquid coexistence curves are shown in reduced units with respect to the theoretical critical density and temperature for Mie potentials with different values in ξ .

FIG. 7: Comparison between two pairs of potentials with same ξ value and almost the same graphical appearance. In (a) Mie (12, 6) and Mie (9.16, 7) with $\xi = 0.89$ are shown. In (b) Mie (8, 6) and Mie (9.29, 5.5) with $\xi = 1.264$ are plotted.

FIG. 8: a) Potentials with same ξ value, 0.89, and different graphical appearance. Mie (12, 6), Mie (20, 5.11), Mie (50, 4.52). b) Vapor-liquid coexistence curves for the potentials shown in a). Densities and temperatures reduced with respect to DPT critical data to show that they do not follow the corresponding states principle.

2. Families of Mie potentials with different ξ value

As for the families of Mie potentials with the same ξ value, there are cases where the potentials with different ξ have almost the same graphical appearance, as for instance the case (14, 7) and (15.58, 6); therefore they will follow a corresponding states behavior. For some Mie potentials with different ξ values and noticeably different graphical appearance, in Fig. 6(b), the coexistence curves of some illustrative cases are shown. Properties are

reduced with respect to the DPT critical data presented in Table III. As can be noticed all curves overlap on a unique curve; suggesting that the corresponding states principle is satisfied for Mie potentials even for different ξ values, at least for the cases considered and based only on a density vs temperature plot. Ramrattan et al.¹⁶ found a similar behavior concerning the vapor-liquid coexistence curves using for their analysis only a pair of cases with $\xi = 0.89$ and a pair of cases with $\xi = 0.521$. Nevertheless we also have found some potentials with different ξ values and noticeably different graphical appearance that do not follow the principle (see Fig. 9).

FIG. 9: a) Potentials with different ξ value and different graphical appearance. b) Temperature-density fluid coexistence curve for two potentials with different ξ value and different graphical appearance that do not follow the corresponding states principle.

B. Saturation pressure–temperature curves

Ramrattan et al.¹⁶ have also analyzed the saturation pressures and they found that corresponding states principle is only followed by systems with the same ξ values. Although DPT critical pressures are not so accurate even for cases with $\xi > 0.85$ presented in Table III, we made an analogous analysis than Ramrattan et al.¹⁶

For potentials with the same ξ in Fig. 10(a), the saturation pressure as a function of temperature is plotted for the same set of fluids of Fig. 6(a). In this Fig. 10(a) the properties are not reduced with respect to the critical ones and as for the case of the vapor–liquid curves, cases with the same ξ overlap into a single curve (as expected since, as mentioned above, for these cases, the shape of the potentials are almost the same for each ξ). This finding is corroborated by using semi-log scale in Fig. 10(c). The same was found by Ramrattan et

al.¹⁶ for other sets of exponents.

In Fig. 10(b), we show the saturation pressures as a function of temperature for some cases with different values of ξ , as in Fig. 6(b). In this plot the variables are reduced with respect to the critical theoretical data. As can be seen, all fluids could be mapped almost in the same universal curve. We also have plotted in semi-log scale these pressures, as in the work of Ramrattan et al.¹⁶ (see Fig. 10(d)). DPT predicts that these potentials follow a corresponding states principle, in disagreement with the findings of Ramrattan et al.¹⁶. We do not know if this discrepancy is due to the limitations of the DPT approach.

FIG. 10: Pressure comparison among different Mie potentials characterized by the factor ξ . (a) Saturated pressure as a function of temperature for Mie potential with same ξ . (b) Saturated pressure as a function of temperature in reduced units with respect to the theoretical critical pressure and temperature for Mie potentials with different values in ξ . (c) and (d) same as in (a) and (b), respectively, in semi-log scale. The curves in (b) and (d) start at the triple point temperatures using the simulation data of Ramrattan et al.¹⁶ for each case.

Summarizing, by considering only the vapor–liquid coexistence curves we found that, for Mie potentials with a fixed or different ξ value, there are two cases: a) potentials whose mathematical expressions are not the same (different exponents) but they have almost the same graphical appearance. For these cases it is evident that they have almost the same thermodynamic properties, and obviously, they will follow a corresponding states principle, and b) potentials with different exponents and different graphical appearance. For these cases there will be some subsets of potentials which follow this principle but in general this does not occur. Concerning the analysis based on the saturation pressures as a function of temperature, the predictions of DPT are not so accurate then it is not possible to give a conclusion on this issue.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Discrete perturbation theory has been implemented for the Mie family fluids and it has been shown that it predicts reliable results for single state supercritical thermodynamic properties and for the vapor-liquid phase diagram when compared with simulation data. The performance of this approach improves for systems whose reduced critical temperatures are greater than one and for $\xi > 0.85$.

Although DPT is not an exact equation of state, it has been useful to question the validity of general conclusions about the corresponding states principle of Mie potentials based only on simulation data (simulations restricted for attractive exponents $\gamma \geq 6$).

From the analysis on temperature–density fluid phase coexistence curves, for $\xi > 0.85$, and for a wider range of exponent values than simulation studies, DPT predicts that in general this principle is not satisfied by Mie (α, γ) potentials. Nevertheless, there are some combinations of Mie exponents for which this principle is satisfied, but not necessarily for cases corresponding to a same ξ value, as suggested by Ramrattan et al.¹⁶. It seems that the parameter ξ is not enough to classify the corresponding states behavior for the whole set of exponents that define Mie potentials.

Finally, we emphasize that DPT approach is not restricted to the Mie cases considered in this work but it can also be applied to a great variety of potentials whose mathematical expressions are known or not and that it is an efficient generator of equations of state. This approach could be improved in the future with the knowledge of more accurate expressions

for the Helmholtz free energy square-well perturbation terms.

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Appendix A: Helmholtz free-energy of the square-well fluid of variable width

In a high-temperature expansion (HTE), the reduced free-energy $a = A/Nk_B T$ for a SW potential with depth ϵ and range λ takes the form

$$a = a^{Id} + a_{HS}(\eta) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{a_n(\eta, \lambda)}{T^{*n}}, \quad (\text{A1})$$

where N is the number of particles, k_B is Boltzmann's constant, T is the absolute temperature, the ideal free-energy $a^{Id} = -1 + \ln \rho + \ln \Lambda^3$, $\Lambda = (h^2/2\pi m k_B T)^{1/2}$ is the thermal wavelength, $a_{HS}(\eta) = (4\eta - 3\eta^2)/(1 - \eta)^2$ is the reduced free-energy of Carnahan-Starling⁶⁰ hard-sphere, the packing fraction $\eta = \pi\rho\sigma^3/6$, $T^* = k_B T/\epsilon$ is the reduced temperature, and the functions $a_n(\eta, \lambda)$ are calculated depending on the range of the potential as is described below.

The thermodynamic properties such as the reduced internal energy $u = U/Nk_B T$ and the compressibility factor $Z = PV/Nk_B T$ can be obtained from the free-energy and the thermodynamic relations

$$u = -T^* \left(\frac{\partial a}{\partial T^*} \right)_{\eta}, \quad Z = \eta \left(\frac{\partial a}{\partial \eta} \right)_{T^*} \quad (\text{A2})$$

which in a HTE can also be expressed as

$$u = \frac{3}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{u_n}{T^{*n}}, \quad Z = 1 + z_{HS}(\eta) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{z_n}{T^{*n}}, \quad (\text{A3})$$

being each $u_n = na_n$ and $z_n = \eta(\partial a_n/\partial \eta)_T$. The reduced free-energy coefficients a_n and the coefficient z_n depending on the variable SW width used in this work will be presented in the next subsections.

1. Intermediate-range expansion

We present the first four perturbation terms as obtained by Espíndola et al.⁵⁰ in a HTE for the free-energy of the square-well system of hard-core diameter σ and range $1 \leq \lambda \leq 3$, Eqs. (A4), (A12), (A20), and (A27), and the first four perturbation terms for a HTE for compressibility factor Z , Eqs. (A11), (A19), (A26), and (A31).

The first coefficient for Eq. (A1) can be expressed as

$$a_1 = \sum_{i=2}^3 \alpha_{i,1}(\lambda) \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right)^{(i-1)} + \sum_{i=1}^4 \gamma_i(\lambda) \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right)^{(i+2)}, \quad (\text{A4})$$

here $\alpha_{2,1}$ and $\alpha_{3,1}$ are given by

$$\alpha_{2,i} = -\frac{2\pi}{3i!}(\lambda^3 - 1), \quad (\text{A5})$$

$$\alpha_{3,1} = -\left(\frac{\pi}{6}\right)^2 \begin{cases} P_1(\lambda), & \lambda \leq 2 \\ P_1(2), & \lambda > 2, \end{cases} \quad (\text{A6})$$

where $P_1(\lambda)$ is the 6th order polynomial

$$P_1(\lambda) = \lambda^6 - 18\lambda^4 + 32\lambda^3 - 15. \quad (\text{A7})$$

As for the γ_n , their expressions are

$$\gamma_n = \gamma_{n,1}\lambda + \gamma_{n,2}\lambda^2 + R_n(\lambda)/Q_n(\lambda), \quad (\text{A8})$$

which are valid for $n \leq 4$ and coefficients $\gamma_{n,j}$ are listed in Table IV, $R_n(\lambda)$ and $Q_n(\lambda)$ are respectively

$$R_n = \gamma_{n,3} + \sum_{j=4}^8 \gamma_{n,j}(\lambda^3 - 1)^{j-2}, \quad (\text{A9})$$

$$Q_n = \gamma_{n,9} + \sum_{j=10}^{14} \gamma_{n,j}(\lambda^3 - 1)^{j-7}. \quad (\text{A10})$$

Therefore, the first coefficient of the compressibility factor is

$$z_1 = \sum_{i=2}^3 (i-1)\alpha_{i,1}(\lambda) \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right)^{(i-1)} + \sum_{i=1}^4 (i+2)\gamma_i(\lambda) \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right)^{(i+2)}. \quad (\text{A11})$$

TABLE IV: $\gamma_{n,j}$ coefficients from Espíndola et al.⁵⁰

j	$\gamma_{1,j}$	$\gamma_{2,j}$	$\gamma_{3,j}$	$\gamma_{4,j}$
1	-59.0464	214.316	-225.479	65.0504
2	26.098	-88.1394	88.8202	-25.096
3	26.4454	273.3	250.472	74.3095
4	7.40136	95.9759	90.2606	26.2153
5	11.0743	71.1228	57.0274	18.4397
6	-5.49152	-40.2656	-33.2376	-10.0891
7	0.781823	5.94069	4.99527	1.50243
8	-0.0319751	-0.23842	-0.195714	-0.057694
9	0.827621	-2.17558	1.84677	-1.87154
10	0.605635	-1.29255	0.99813	-1.01682
11	-0.254959	0.554993	-0.440314	0.445247
12	0.0377111	-0.0857543	0.0708793	-0.0725107
13	-0.00210896	0.00492511	-0.00416274	0.00427862
14	0.0000452328	-0.000107067	0.0000917291	-0.0000949723

The second coefficient for Eq. (A1) is given by

$$a_2 = \chi(\eta, \lambda) \exp \left[\xi_2(\lambda) \frac{6\eta}{\pi} + \varphi_1(\lambda) \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi} \right)^3 + \varphi_2(\lambda) \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi} \right)^4 \right], \quad (\text{A12})$$

with

$$\chi = \alpha_{2,2}(\lambda) \frac{6\eta}{\pi} \left(1 - \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi} \right)^2 / 1.5129 \right), \quad (\text{A13})$$

where $\alpha_{2,2}$ is given by Eq. (A5) and the functions φ_i , $i = 1, 2$ are

$$\varphi_i = \sum_{n=0}^7 \varphi_{i,n} \lambda^n, \quad (\text{A14})$$

whose coefficients $\varphi_{i,n}$ are listed in Table V. The function ξ_2 is given by

$$\xi_2 = \alpha_{3,2}(\lambda) / \alpha_{2,2}(\lambda), \quad (\text{A15})$$

the term $\alpha_{3,2}$ is

$$\alpha_{3,2} = \left(\frac{\pi}{6}\right)^2 \begin{cases} P_2(\lambda) - P_1(\lambda)/2, & \lambda \leq 2 \\ -17/2 + P_4(\lambda), & \lambda > 2. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A16})$$

P_1 is the polynomial given by Eq. (A7), P_2 and P_4 are polynomials defined as

$$P_2(\lambda) = -2\lambda^6 + 36\lambda^4 - 32\lambda^3 - 18\lambda^2 + 16, \quad (\text{A17})$$

$$P_4(\lambda) = 32\lambda^3 - 18\lambda^2 - 48. \quad (\text{A18})$$

Consequently, the second coefficient of the compressibility factor is

$$z_2 = a_2 \left[1 + \xi_2(\lambda) \frac{6\eta}{\pi} + 3\varphi_1(\lambda) \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right)^3 + 4\varphi_2(\lambda) \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right)^4 \right] - 2\alpha_{22} \left(\left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right)^3 / 1.5129 \right) \exp \left[\xi_2(\lambda) \frac{6\eta}{\pi} + \varphi_1(\lambda) \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right)^3 + \varphi_2(\lambda) \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right)^4 \right]. \quad (\text{A19})$$

TABLE V: $\varphi_{n,j}$ and $\theta_{3,j}$ coefficients from Espíndola et al.⁵⁰

j	$\varphi_{1,j}$	$\varphi_{2,j}$	$\theta_{3,j}$	$\theta_{4,j}$
0	-1320.19	1049.76	—	—
1	5124.1	-4023.29	-945.597	4131.09
2	-8145.37	6305.95	1326.61	-10501.1
3	6895.8	-5265.42	-471.688	8909.18
4	-3381.42	2553.84	—	-2521.96
5	968.739	-727.3	23.2271	-16.7882
6	-151.255	113.631	-2.63477	19.5315
7	9.98592	-7.56266	—	-1.27373

The third coefficient a_3 is given by

$$a_3 = \alpha_{2,3} \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right) \exp \left[\xi_3 \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right) + K_3(\eta, \lambda) \right], \quad (\text{A20})$$

where $K_3(\eta, \lambda)$ is

$$K_3(\eta, \lambda) = \frac{\left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right)^2 \sum_{n=1}^4 \theta_{3,n} \lambda^n}{1 + \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right) \sum_{n=5}^7 \theta_{3,n} \lambda^{n-4}}. \quad (\text{A21})$$

and the coefficients $\theta_{3,n}$ are contained in Table V. The function ξ_3 is given by

$$\xi_3 = \alpha_{3,3}(\lambda)/\alpha_{2,3}(\lambda), \quad (\text{A22})$$

where $\alpha_{2,3}$ is given by Eq. (A5) and $\alpha_{3,3}$ is

$$\alpha_{3,3} = \left(\frac{\pi}{6}\right)^2 \begin{cases} P_2(\lambda) - P_1(\lambda)/6 - P_3(\lambda), & \lambda \leq 2 \\ -17/6 + P_4(\lambda) - P_5(\lambda), & \lambda > 2. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A23})$$

P_1 , P_2 , and P_4 are given by Eqs. (A7), (A17), and (A18), respectively, while P_3 and P_5 are defined by

$$P_3(\lambda) = 6\lambda^6 - 18\lambda^4 + 18\lambda^2 - 6, \quad (\text{A24})$$

$$P_5(\lambda) = 5\lambda^6 - 32\lambda^3 + 18\lambda^2 + 26. \quad (\text{A25})$$

Now, the third coefficient of the compressibility factor takes the form

$$z_3 = a_3 \left[1 + \xi_3 \frac{6\eta}{\pi} + \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right)^2 \sum_{n=1}^4 \theta_{3,n} \lambda^n \frac{2 + \frac{6\eta}{\pi} \sum_{n=5}^7 \theta_{3,n} \lambda^{n-4}}{\left(1 + \frac{6\eta}{\pi} \sum_{n=5}^7 \theta_{3,n} \lambda^{n-4}\right)^2} \right]. \quad (\text{A26})$$

The fourth coefficient for the free-energy expansion Eq. (A1) is given by

$$a_4 = \alpha_{2,4} \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right) \exp \left[\xi_4 \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right) + K_4(\eta, \lambda) \right], \quad (\text{A27})$$

here, $K_4(\eta, \lambda)$ is

$$K_4(\eta, \lambda) = \frac{\left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right)^2 \sum_{n=1}^4 \theta_{4,n} \lambda^n}{1 + \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right) \sum_{n=5}^7 \theta_{4,n} \lambda^{n-4}}. \quad (\text{A28})$$

and the coefficients $\theta_{4,n}$ are in Table V. The function ξ_4 is defined as

$$\xi_4 = \alpha_{3,4}(\lambda)/\alpha_{2,4}(\lambda), \quad (\text{A29})$$

where $\alpha_{2,4}$ is given by Eq. (A5) and $\alpha_{3,4}$ is

$$\alpha_{3,4} = \left(\frac{\pi}{6}\right)^2 \begin{cases} -P_1(\lambda)/24 + 7P_2(\lambda)/12 - 3P_3(\lambda)/2, & \lambda \leq 2 \\ -17/24 + 7P_4(\lambda)/12 - 3P_5(\lambda)/2, & \lambda > 2. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A30})$$

P_1 to P_5 are given by Eqs. (A7), (A17), (A24), (A18), and (A25) respectively.

Finally, the fourth coefficient of the compressibility factor is

$$z_4 = a_4 \left[1 + \xi_4 \frac{6\eta}{\pi} + \left(\frac{6\eta}{\pi}\right)^2 \sum_{n=1}^4 \theta_{4,n} \lambda^n \frac{2 + \frac{6\eta}{\pi} \sum_{n=5}^7 \theta_{4,n} \lambda^{n-4}}{\left(1 + \frac{6\eta}{\pi} \sum_{n=5}^7 \theta_{4,n} \lambda^{n-4}\right)^2} \right]. \quad (\text{A31})$$

2. Long-range expansion

First and second perturbation terms for a HTE for free-energy of the square-well fluid of hard-core diameter σ and range $\lambda > 3$, Eqs. (A32) and (A35), and the first two-order perturbation terms for a HTE for compressibility factor Z , Eqs. (A34) and (A38), are presented.

The first coefficient $a_1(\eta, \lambda)$ in the long-range region, $\lambda > 3$, has been explored by del Ro and Lira⁴⁷ and it takes the form:

$$a_1 = a_{vdW} + (1 - K)/2, \quad (\text{A32})$$

where $a_{vdW} = -4\eta\lambda^3$ and K is the compressibility of the HS system.

$$K = \frac{(1 - \eta)^4}{1 + 4\eta + 4\eta^2 - 4\eta^3 + \eta^4}. \quad (\text{A33})$$

Therefore, the first term for the compressibility factor is

$$z_1 = a_{vdW} - \frac{2\eta(1 - \eta)^3(\eta^2 - 5\eta - 2)}{(1 + 4\eta + 4\eta^2 - 4\eta^3 + \eta^4)^2}. \quad (\text{A34})$$

The second term $a_2(\eta, \lambda)$ obtained by Benavides and del Ro⁵³ can be expressed as

$$a_2(\eta, \lambda) = \alpha_3(\eta)\lambda^3 + \alpha_2(\eta)\lambda^2 + \alpha_0(\eta) \quad (\text{A35})$$

with coefficients

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_3(\eta) &= -2\eta K^2, \\ \alpha_2(\eta) &= 72\eta^2 b_3(\eta, 0) - f_1(\eta), \\ \alpha_0(\eta) &= -(\eta/8)[48\eta b_5(\eta, 0) + \eta K^2 K_{\eta\eta} + 2K^2 K_\eta] - f_2(\eta). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A36})$$

where the functions $b_3(\eta, 0)$, $b_5(\eta, 0)$, $f_1(\eta)$, and $f_2(\eta)$ are

$$\begin{aligned} b_3(\eta, 0) &= (7\eta^5 - 62\eta^4 + 229\eta^3 - 421\eta^2 + 260\eta - 175)/700(1 + 2\eta)^3, \\ b_5(\eta, 0) &= (-756\eta^8 + 17130\eta^7 - 101255\eta^6 + 297700\eta^5 - 518840\eta^4 \\ &\quad + 557372\eta^3 - 346930\eta^2 + 117500\eta - 10500)/63000(1 + 2\eta)^5, \\ f_1(\eta) &= 1152\eta^3(6/\pi)(-\pi/70 + 0.542606\eta - 3.603485\eta^2 + 15.98034\eta^3 \\ &\quad - 47.5036\eta^4 + 89.215318\eta^5 - 94.365168\eta^6 + 42.480471\eta^7), \\ f_2(\eta) &= 1152\eta^3(6/\pi)(\pi/567 - 0.1201327\eta + 1.14030\eta^2 - 5.853621\eta^3 \\ &\quad + 16.57782\eta^4 - 24.037283\eta^5 + 13.799866\eta^6). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A37})$$

Here, K , K_η , and $K_{\eta\eta}$ are the reduced compressibility, the first and the second derivative with respect to η .

The second term in the compressibility factor expansion is

$$z_2 = \eta(\alpha'_3(\eta)\lambda^3 + \alpha'_2(\eta)\lambda^2 + \alpha'_0(\eta)), \quad (\text{A38})$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha'_3(\eta) &= -2K^2 - 4\eta K K_\eta, \\ \alpha'_2(\eta) &= 144\eta b_3(\eta, 0) + 72\eta^2 b'_3(\eta, 0) - f'_1(\eta), \\ \alpha'_0(\eta) &= -f'_2(\eta) - (1/8)[48\eta b_5(\eta, 0) + \eta K^2 K_{\eta\eta} + 2K^2 K_\eta] \\ &\quad - \frac{\eta}{8}[48(\eta b'_5 + b_5) + 3K^2 K_{\eta\eta} + 4K K_\eta^2 + 2\eta K K_\eta K_{\eta\eta} + \eta K^2 K_{\eta\eta\eta}]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A39})$$

Here, the tilde denotes derivative with respect to η .

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